

Women's Different Agencies in the Gupta Age: An Inscriptional Study

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ABSTRACT

The Gupta Empire was established by Shri-Gupta in 319-20 AD. Gupta rulers adopted marriage alliance diplomacy as a significant part of the Gupta empire foreign policy. It helped in the consolidation of the Gupta empire. In this regard, various royal women played important roles in the making of the Gupta Empire through matrimonial alliances, such as Kumaradevi, Prabhavtigupta, Dhuramadevi, and Kubernaga. Earliest studies did not pay much attention to making the women visible on the historical stage, Later feminist historians gave their attention to the issue. But they did leave again Gupta women undiscovered in historical sources (mainly Inscription). The article explores both royal and lay women's different agencies such as political, religious, economic and cultural. The primary sources are Gupta inscriptions (Fleet, 1960) in collaboration coins and texts that are also used to make references. The main secondary sources are Archaeological Sources of India various reports, Epigraphia Indica reports and texts.

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Introduction

In ancient India, a number of magnificent kings had established their glory by their political agency. They contributed in different ways to make their appearance in history. In early history writings,

scholars mainly focused on the political history of empires. In these writings, they mainly documented royal men. They overlooked women's contributions in empire building and other fields. If we look at ancient Indian history few women find in place only in a symbolic and precise manner. However, in reality, several royal women exercised their political, economic, religious and cultural agency.

Ancient Indian society was patriarchal in nature like today.

Ancient Indian texts and archaeological sources tell us that in Ancient India several intellectual women existed, which exercised political, social, religious and economic agency. They come mainly from elite or royal sections. There are a few royal women examples which exercised their agency such as Prabhavtigupta (Gupta-Vakataka), queen Sembiyan (Chola), Didda (queen of Kashmir), Rudramma (queen of the Kakatiyas). These royal ladies wielded much power in the state as the regent queen for their son. The evidence suggests that Rajyasri sister of Harasvardhan also active in court politics. Queen Sembiyan was an important figure in the Chola empire. Apart from royal women, epigraphical evidence suggests that several lay women too participated in public work and exercised their agencies.

Altekar states that women participated in different forms like Women authors, philosophers, doctors and, teachers Lopamudra, Ghosa were composers of Vedas, Gargi, Maitreyi. The royal ladies were provided education, military and administrative training (Altekar, 1962). Kalidas in *Abhigyan Shakuntalam* states that royal women were given education. Rulings families girls received military and administrative training like Nayanika (Sathavana), Prabhavtigupta (Gupta), Vijayabhatrika (Chalukya), and Didda (Kashmir) (Altekar, 1962). Their administrative efficiency suggests they were provided several skills and knowledge necessary to live better lives mentioned by Vatsyayna as sixty-four arts (Upadhyaya, 1961). Vatsyayana's *Kamasutra* lists 64 arts, encompassing a wide range of skills and knowledge, from performing arts like music and dance to more practical arts like cooking and crafting.

The proposed article will explore the political, economic, religious and cultural agencies of the Gupta women. The role of royal women was important in the making of a mighty empire in ancient India which is known as the imperial Gupta. Through different means, women played important roles such as marriage alliances, decision-making, participation in state affairs, donors, public works. The primary source is inscriptions of the Gupta period but literary sources are also explored for references. Several secondary sources belonging to the theme have been explored.

Literature Review

Women's History is indispensable and essential to the emancipation of women. Greda Learner is a prominent feminist writer who has written extensively about the origin of patriarchal institutions. She points out that the history of women was not paid much attention in earlier writings. History writing of ancient India is reflected mainly from viewpoint of men. G. Learner has explained that the written history belongs to half race (Learner, 1986). Peter Burke says 'history from below, Women's history offers a new perspective on the past. Stating the objects of history concerned solely with women, Joan Kelly Gadol says, 'women's history has a dual goal: to restore women to history and to restore our history to women'.

As far as the Gupta period is concerned, we have not come across any work relating to women based on epigraphic evidence. Indian Feminist scholars consider that androcentric views are persisted by Altekar's ideal hood the ancient women model in which he idealised women's status without any critical interpretation (Altekar, 1962). He gives several selected examples to prove his point such as Gargi and Ghosha. Later, the Feminist movement in India challenged and criticised the traditional history writing approach. Firstly, Uma Chakaravarti challenged Altekar's women's ideal hood model widely and said we need to think beyond the Altekar Ghost (Roy, 1999). She further said he picked several selected examples such as Gargi, Ghosa and others. Other prominent historians who are writing on ancient Indian women are Kumkum Roy, Upinder Singh, K.K. Shah, and L Orr. Who have written about women different aspects. Kumkum Roy worked on male and female donors comparison of the Sanchi region is significant. She finds in her analysis that both donors are considerably equal in nature. K.K. Shah's work is significant he tried to identify multiple Identities of women in inscriptions, and he explored mainly four categories royal, religious, familial and professional women. The work is very significant (Shah, 2001) V.L. Singh argues that the earlier writings show women in subordinated positions. She highlighted several royal women who played important roles in ancient India (Singh, 2015). L. Orr explored inscriptions of the Tamil region to make women visible on the historical stage. She tried to explore different roles of women as religious identity priests, monks and ascetics. L. Orr also tried to women in South Indian inscriptions. L. Orr's work is significant on temple women during the Chola period (Orr, 2000).

V. Krishnamoorty's work on inscriptions to make women visible on historical path is significant. She divides her findings into three categories namely; Family women, Prostitutes and Courtesan. Aloka

Parasar and Aparna Basu explored inscriptions to make women visible on the historical path. Early historiography of women was led by nationalist and colonial writers, they did not provide women much attention in their writings. They seem to be affected by ideologies. Uma Chakarvarti argued that nationalist historians responded to colonial scholars. R. Bharadwaj Gupta's work on Gupta Coins has been an important work. She has tried to explore the cultural aspects of the Gupta coins. She further analysed that the King-Queen coin type confirmed queens enjoyed great respect during the Gupta period. Samudragupta-Queens time coins show importance of the queen. In one coin she has been shown sitting on a couch and appeared to be discussing some important administrative affairs. Anvita Anand, Gupta Kal Mai Nariyon ki Isthti is an important work, though it seems to be an overview (Anand, 1990).

H. Chakarborti, India as reflected in the Inscriptions of the Gupta period work is significant he tried to explore social, political, religious and administrative aspects of the Gupta empire, yet women's issues were ignored by the writer (Chakarborti, 1978). In ancient India, a lot of work has been done on texts to resurface women identities but inscriptions have been not explored yet in totality especially belongs to the Gupta period. So I here tried to fill this gap to make the Gupta era women's different agencies visible on the historical stage.

Gupta Royal Women In Different Agencies

Historical evidence tells us that several royal women had left their imprint on the historical stage. The main figures are Kumaradevi, Prabhavatigupta, Dhurmadevi, Kashmir Queen Didda, Nayanika (Sathvahana) and Sembiyan (Chola). They exercised agency in different ways. As regent queen, constructor, donor, gift-making, philanthropic and public welfare and through court politics. At that time prevalent political model of ruling was the monarchical order. The patriarchal social order was prevalent.

The Gupta period as was the Golden era in Indian history due to remarkable development in art and literature. The literature tells us that smritis imposed several restrictions on women. Several texts claim that the royal ladies were entitled to receive education and training in liberal arts such as dance, painting, and art. Texts confirm that lower class-women had more freedom to make a livelihood compared to elite women. In this setup, most women are subordinated, but there are several royal or elite class women, who had got opportunity to exercise agency as queens, intellectuals, artists, and poets, regents queens,

regent sons, They all provide us with an alternative to the androcentric as women perspective (Learner, 1986). These women played important role in the course of events and in shaping history. These undocumented or less documented women need to be made visible on the historical stage.

The inscriptions of the Gupta period reveal women's multiple identities. Gupta Inscriptions and the art material are the crucial source for making women visible on historical stage. They reflect different things about their agency, economic power, religious and cultural beliefs, practices, and their contribution to the making of the Gupta Empire through the matrimonial alliances policy, court politics, and governance. In this category women being the most important are Kumaradevi, Parbhavatigupta, Kubernaga and Rudhrmadevi. These were married through matrimonial alliances and played an important role in consolidating the Gupta Empire. They contributed in many ways to make the Gupta empire strong, stable and larger in area.

Matrimonial alliances were commonly prevalent in royal families throughout history. It was a political instrument to establish friendly and familial relations. This Matrimonial diplomacy was earlier used by the Mauryas, Shungas, and Kushanas. We also found matrimonial alliances references in texts such as Vedas, Puranas and epics Ramayana and Mahabharata.

The Gupta Empire was founded in 319-20 AD by Sri Gupta (Fleet, 1960). The archaeological sources suggest that he did not adopt the matrimonial alliances as state policy. Chandargupta 1 was the important king of the Gupta empire. The Gupta Inscriptions and King Queen-type gold coins confirmed that he was married to a Licchavi princess named Kumaradevi (Anand, 1970). Mahadevi Kumaradevi was Chandragupta 1 chief queen and belongs to the Licchavi clan of the Himalayan foothills, in modern days the territory falls under Nepal. She was married to Chandragupta-1 through the marriage diplomacy. This step helped Chandragupta 1 to expand and consolidate the Gupta empire. It expanded territorial boundaries, and economic and military resources and established peaceful borders in the Northern side of Magadha. Marriage diplomacy was a significant part of Gupta's foreign policy. Several archaeological sources indicate that several Gupta women enjoyed administrative officers power such as Kumaradevi, and Prabhavatigupta (Altekar, 1962).

According to several scholars, these matrimonial alliances were the result of well-calculated foreign policy and had political and economic advantages. After the Gupta alliance with Licchvi dynasty empire extended in the northern region to the Himalayan foothills. It made the Gupta Empire stable, more

powerful, and expanded territorial boundaries (Anand, 1970). Before Chandergupta 1, Gupta emperors held the title of *Maharaj*, after this alliance Chandergupta held lofty titles such as *Maharajadhiraj*. So these claims confirm Gupta Empire benefited from this policy (Prabhat, 2007).

In a Gupta coin Kumaradevi shown sitting on a couch indicates her political influence was considerable. She is well ornamented and dressed. She is talking to Chandragupta 1. It look like they were discussing an important matter. Several Gupta feudatory women also made great footprints which are recorded in the inscriptions. Almost every King had multiple wives. It indicates that polygamy was widely prevalent among royal families. They were known as chief queen, second wife and mistress (Fleet, 1960).

The title used in inscriptions as the chief and secondary shows their status, hierarchy and the respect they received from the king. Kumaradevi was the chief queen of Chandragupta 1. She got the highest honour from her husband. The king-queen types coins of Chandragupta 1 confirm this statement loudly. An inscription records the marriage of Chandragupta 1 with Kumaradevi. Multiple identities come out by inscriptions of women as queen, mother, daughter and wife (Fleet, 1960).

The Allahabad Inscriptions of Samudragupta records a princess named Samharika. She was probably his daughter. Although, in the Gupta period patriarchy was the social reality. According to Monarchy rule usually the eldest son succession gets empire to rule or ascend. But it did not happen always, history tells us that sometimes there were intense struggles between princes for succession. In the Gupta period itself, there was a civil war.

In the Gupta period, a technical term '*Mahadevi*' title was used to refer to royal women, which means the '*great Goddess*' (Fleet, 1960). It was a way to show respect towards royal women. The epigraphical records show that different titles were used for other women. It indicates that status of hierarchy was prevalent. Even queens are referred to as chief and secondary queen. The deep analysis of historical and literary sources tells us that the king participated in the war and won territories other side royal women exercised their agencies through different ways such as court politics, gifts, philanthropy, donations, public welfare and temple construction.

'*Lichchhavi Dauithitra*' terms is mentioned in the Samudragupta Prayag Prashasti also known as the Allahabad Pillar Inscription. The phrase shows respect for the Licchavi princess Kumaradevi wife of Chandragupta. She was mother of Samudragupta. The Eran stone pillar inscription of Samudragupta has immense value from the women's point of view. The inscription records that he was married to a faithful

wife (EI-14, 1982). The inscription suggests a profound ethical value of the queen's possession. Several times inscriptions had contradictory views compared to contemporary texts. In this case, Inscriptions seem to be more liberated than texts towards women.

Dhruvadevi was the wife of Chandragupta 2. She possibly instigated Chandragupta 2 to take military campaign, a seal from the Basarh indicates she ruled as a provincial leader, probably active in court politics (Fleet, 1960). Dhruvadevi had exercised agency efficiently. She was the mother of Kumargupta 1. The Basarh seal suggests that she acted as consort queen to influence Chandragupta's decision. Archaeological sources indicate that she was stimulated to take a military campaign. According to Devi-Chandarguptam play Dhruvadevi earlier was wife of Chandargupta 1 brother Ramagupta. She later married to Chandragupta.

The Bhitari stone pillar inscription of Skandagupta records multiple identities of women (EI-12, 1982). The Inscriptions also reflected their religious beliefs and practices. A number of coins record different Goddesses along with the holy river Goddess. The inscription of Skandagupta, records the river Goddess Gangā. Several river goddesses are frequently mentioned in the Gupta era inscriptions. They also suggest their religious beliefs. A number of coins record different Goddesses along with the holy river Goddess. The Inscription records different identities of women with their names as Kumaradevi, Dattadevi, and Dhruvadevi. They reflect mother, daughter, and wife identities. Besides this, it also records several religious figures such as Devki and the River Goddess Ganga. It is interesting that Gupta several rulers documented their family women in historical records.

The Gangadhar stone inscription of Visvarman mentioned different identities and activities of women. The inscription belongs to the Gupta feudatories from Malwa region. The inscriptions record lovely women of enemies and mistresses. Their wives with different ornaments. This thing suggests that women were fond of jewellery. The Gupta sculptures reflect different types of jewellery adorned by women. The inscription further records that a young lady destroyed their enemies. It shows the prowess qualities of women and participation in war. She must have been some kind of agency. Different identities which were mentioned are mistresses, lovely women of the gods, female ghouls, and Divine mothers. The inscription possesses great historical value. The Inscription records different types of women agencies.

The Eran posthumous stone pillar inscription of Goparaja has significant historical value. It is the first historical evidence of the Sati tradition dated 510 AD (Fleet, 1960). However, the example of the Sati practices we found earlier in texts. In literature form, the first Sati tradition example comes into our knowledge from the Rigveda possible. According to the inscription Bhanugupta's wife performed Sati practice on her husband's funeral pyre. The sati practice was prevalent in the warrior class and elite sections of women. However, it was not performed by every women. Prabhavati Gupta after becoming widowed performed as regent queen for her son's other side Dhruvadevi remarried to Chandargupta 2 after her husband Ramgupta's death.

The copper plate inscription of the Maharaja Sarvanatha records the long family genealogy. In which his mother and father both mentioned. The inscriptions also suggest about his religious beliefs. They worshipped divine goddesses and performed rituals (Fleet, 1960). The inscriptions are a crucial source of social, cultural, and religious information.

In Gupta and their sovereign or feudatory inscriptions, different identities of women come out. Divine, royal and laywomen are main classifications. Among different goddesses are reflected important being as Goddesses of royalty, Sri, Saraswati sovereignty. Sometimes their appearance is described in textual form (Fleet, 1960). The Inscriptions record gifts and donations are given to Brahmanas in the marriage of daughters.

An inscription records that a Queen named *Mahadei* Srimatī built a religious college to spread religious knowledge. It is a significant knowledge which comes out through inscriptions. It suggests that she had political, religious and economic agency. She was the wife of Gupta feudatories. Another woman named Konadevi excavated a wonderful tank. Konadevi participated in public welfare work. Another woman named Ijjadevi issues an order—but unfortunately inscription record is not complete and damaged over time. But she might have been influential and had agency. From these historical records, different agencies of women come to light. These records suggest that women had agency and participated in different kinds of things to make an appearance in public through their philanthropic works (Fleet, 1960).

The Sarnath stone inscription of Prarakaditya records his mother and wifely identities. The inscription further claims the religious purpose of his mother Paramadevi allotted. This indicates her religious agency. Several inscriptions indicate that royal women made religious donations to get religious merit.

In the Gupta inscriptions technical titles were used for wives of Maharajas, such as *Mahadevi*, and *Paramadevi* (Fleet, 1960) Several technical titles were used to refer to royal women. *Mahadevi* means great goddess and *Paramadevi* means supreme goddess. Such titles used for royal women suggest that they enjoyed respect in the eyes of kings. These things reflect their economic and political power.

A copper plate records a grant by Dharmamahādēvī wife of Santikara, king of Kongada-mandala (ASI, 1925-26). These grants show that royal women had an important role in administration. The Stupa of Bharut pillars discloses significant information about agency of women. A sculpture represents a woman riding a horse. The sculpture suggests she might have been from an aristocratic background. It also reflects her feminine power. Her horse riding skill also reflects her military agency. Texts also records that royal women given military training.

Licchavi princess Kumāradevī was married to Chandragupta. The marriage was part of the matrimonial diplomacy which had a propounding impact on the Gupta empire consolidation in northern India. The archaeological sources confirmed Chandragupta married to Kumaradevi. In several coins, Kumaradevi is represented sitting on couch along with the king. It indicates several things such as; her position, agency and importance.

Prabhāvātī was the daughter of Chandragupta 2. She was married to the Vakataka prince Rudrasen 2. Her husband died at a young age thereafter Prabhavatigupta ruled as regent queen. According to the sources she ruled almost for twenty years. During her reign, she made land grants to several Brahmanas. It shows her economic agency and she had an interest in religious matters. Prabhavtigupta Poona copper plate inscriptions provide several important historical data about her reign. Her marriage was part of a marriage diplomacy scheme. In her inscription, she records her genealogy as the Gupta side, not the Vakataka side. Royal ladies like Prabhavati wielded much power in the state. (Bhasam, 2022) During this time and in this part of the sub-continent the land grant and maintenance of a was at the same time an act of political, economic, social and religious agency. The Poona copper plate inscription further records that she made a land grant to her family Guru. She also made maintenance for it.

Political marriages helped the Guptas to expand to large territory in two ways; Limit their enemies and Expand their army and military strength. There are several key points which are reflected in the Prabhavatigupta Poona copper plate such as she used Gupta genealogy instead of Vakatakas, she used her father Chandragupta-2 gotra instead of Vakataka, she used Gupta script instead of Vakatakas.

Prabhavati Gupta had maintained friendly relations with the Gupta empire and also sought guidance from her father. Prabhavati Gupta's rule in the south provided the Gupta Empire stability at the southern front. Gupta emperors adopted a well-calculated marriage diplomacy and it was an important part of their foreign policy. Marriage alliance has several advantages or Importance. Chandragupta- Kumaradevi: this marriage alliance with the Licchavi tribe manifoldly benefited the empire, provided more resources, friendly relations with another tribe, more economic sources, territory expanded, emperors peace of mind from this side.

Prabhavati Gupta married to the Vakataka prince after her husband's death she ruled the dynasty under the guidance of her father till her son got it. Established friendly relations, and helped in expanding in the south. Sometimes she worked as a regent queen until her son reached maturity level to assume office legally. The inscription indicates that she played an important role in administration and policymaking. Prabhavati Gupta Poona copper plate shows he granted land to her family Guru. In Gupta coins, queen Kumaradevi appeared with her husband in different poses over coins. In one significant representation, she appeared to be sitting on a couch and discussing important affairs. The Gupta empire marriage alliances seems to be beneficial for empire expansion peacefully in many ways. The Daodarpur Copper Plates of the Gupta Period is a significant historical sources. The Inscription records Kumaragupta's chief queen was Ānanda-Dēvī. It also records the Gupta genealogy in detail.

The Poona copper plate inscription of Prabhavati Gupta. It had been only an inscription from the Gupta period which was recorded by a woman. It is a significant inscriptions. The inscription records that Prabhavati Gupta made a land grant to her family Guru. The inscription is also known as the Rihpur copper plate. The Poona Plates of Vakataka Queen Prabhavati Gupta further records a grant made by Prabhavati Gupta, chief wife of Rudrasena 2, daughter of Chandergupta-2, and mother of Divakara Sen. She ruled as Queen mother (EI-14, 1982). Throw light on the Vakataka-Gupta relations. The Inscription records she had belief in Devine figure. Samudragupta's mother Kumaradevi daughter of the Licchavi tribe's head. Also indicate their identity, family, and matrimonial relations impacts.

The Poona plates of the Vakataka Queen Prabhavati Gupta have immense historical value. The Inscription reveals the different identities of Prabhavati Gupta such as chief queen, daughter, and Mother. She had authority and agency (EI-15, 1982). Prabhavati was a regent of her son, she and her father interfered in the Vakataka administration. She had used Gupta gotra, genealogy and script

(Prabhat, 2007). She ruled almost for twenty years. She ruled efficiently with good governance and made donations for religious purpose and land grant.

Several queens directly participated in the administration. So they certainly influenced day-to-day policies. In several coins, Kumardevi is shown on the coins with her husband sitting on the couch. It shows importance and power she enjoyed. She belongs to the Lichchhvi tribes. Through matrimonial alliances, Kumardevi helped to expand the Gupta empire. It also secured the northern border and established a peaceful relationship between both royal families. We can assume that these matrimonial alliances had an important role in empire-building. They had consolidated the Gupta empire. The matrimonial alliance's instrument was a well-calculated part of foreign policy during ancient India. It helped manifold to the monarchies to expand, enlarge, increase power, prestige, resources, stability and military strength (Prabhat, 2007).

Lay Women in different Agencies

The archaeological and literary sources mainly talk about royal or elite women's agencies. There are a few examples which also talk about lay women and give us critical information about them. Although, they are small in numbers but significant information about lay women in different agencies. Altekar says lower classes women are working and involved in different work. There were attendants, cauri-bearers, doorkeepers, and visual sources also confirmed these claims. Women are shown in sculptures in different forms. In the Gupta period women temples women are shown as doorkeepers and attendants. River goddesses Ganga and Yamuna sculptures from Ahichchatra clearly represented attendants along with the river goddess.

The Mandsaur Inscriptions of the Malwa region have been the significant historical sources from the point of view of women perspective. Mandsaur city was located in the Malwa region. The inscriptions recorded the different activities of lay women. It describes the parks of the city of Mandsaur was full of women, moving freely in large numbers or singing perpetually, showing thereby the gleeful mood and free movement of women in the Gupta age (Chakarborti, 1978) Singing and dancing were the professions adopted by women in those days in return they received money or things it is not clear but one thing is clearly suggest they would have been economically better compared to inside-home women. The city is charming. Women were singing, dancing and moving freely in the city gardens (Fleet, 1960). The Mandsaur inscriptions of Gupta feudatories record that Mandsaur's garden was full of women. The

inscription indicates that women had autonomy. It also indicates the leisure aspect of that time. Women are involved in different types of entertainment to get refresh. Mandsaur inscriptions of Gupta feudatories record that Mandsaur's garden was full of women. They were dancing, enjoying and moving freely (EI-12, 1982) The aspect of leisure is reflected here. In ancient India, people tried different things to entertain themselves such as dancing, singing, horse riding, playing, etc, It also shows women's social status and freedom. The inscription also records the daughter and mother identities of women.

The Sanchi Inscription records several significant things. The Buddhist inscription records that a woman named Hari Swamini had granted money to someone. She was the wife of Sanasidha. She made a religious gift. It also indicates that Hari swamini had an interest in religious and cultural matters. An inscription records a woman headed a religious institution as *Vihara svamini* (a lady superintendent of the Vihara) was a religious post which was held by a lady (EI-12, 1982). The Inscription shows that women-led different kinds of works which were traditionally in the domain of men. They established religious education college, public work, excavated tank and headed religious institutions, so it suggests that women had Agency in different fields. Women exercised their political, religious, economic and cultural agency through public works. Women exercised different agencies through public generosity, piety, building alliances in court or marriage, philanthropy, public gifts, gifts, donations, land grants, temple construction, public welfare water tank construction and maintenance.

In the Gupta period Prostitution, ganika and courtesan were important part of urban life. They earned their livelihood. They were ladies of wealth, possessing great influence, and royal favour (Tyagi, 1994). Kumkum Roy argues that prostitution enjoyed economic agency compared to traditional women which were confined within household boundaries. They had considerable wealth. State imposed tax on their profession. Sometimes they had considerable political support. They were bound not by social norms and restrictions and had liberty compared to familial class women. Some prostitutes were wealthy, intelligent and had considerable political support. They were protected by the state. (Kumkum Roy, 2023). In the Maurya period, a dedicated officer was appointed to protect them named as Superintendent of Prostitutes. The ganika class of prostitution was considered rich (Desai, 1985). Sudraka defined Vasantasena as wealthy, brave and with refined taste. She was portrayed as a powerful and brave figure in Sudraka's Mricchakatika. Vasantsena was a wealthy courtesan who fell in love with the impoverished Brahmin Charudatta. Vasantsena was portrayed as brave woman who challenged patriarchal norms. In Jainism and Buddhism, several women lived their live as ascetics, nuns and renunciates normal life.

They were challenged social norms. They lived as Bhikkuni and nuns apart from family life. They directly challenged normal social life order, though, examples are few.

Nagar Vadhu was a professional dancer, entertainer and singer (Anand, 1970). In the Gupta period, a Nagarvadhu (bride of the city) was a public woman, often of exceptional beauty and talent, who was recognised for her skills in dance and music and considered a symbol of grace and sophistication. She was a form of royal courtesan, and her presence was valued for entertainment and appreciation by the elite, particularly kings. She was appreciated by the wealthy and powerful section of the society for her various skills. Amrapali was a famous Nagarvadhu of Vaishali in the Gupta period. She was known for her beauty, talent, and the significant wealth she amassed through her performances. The Nagarvadhu tradition highlights a unique aspect of ancient Indian society, where women were recognised for their skills and beauty, and public entertainment was a respected part of court life.

Women in the Gupta period also participated in Agriculture and labour activities. Yajnavalkya Smriti states women used to make living through crafts, spinning and sewing. Mainly lower class women were engaged in these type of works. Lower-class women had considerable mobility to earn their livelihood compared to upper-class women. Yajnavalkya Smriti defined Stridhan as gifts received by close relatives. This property could include jewellery, clothing, and even certain rights to land. The woman had ownership rights to her stridhan. It was given to the girl at the time of marriage. The Pardah practice was not the part of the Gupta society (Anand, 1970). We can make an analysis from the texts and visual sources of the Gupta period that Pardah practice was not prevalent in this period. Visual sources show that women are participating in processions without Pardah.

Conclusion

To conclude on the basis of Gupta inscriptions, we can say that several Gupta elite women exercised their political, economic, religious and cultural agency. They had played an important role in the consolidation of the Gupta empire. Gupta rulers had adopted matrimonial alliances as a significant part of their foreign policy. It helped them in territorial expansion, prestige, and power culmination. Apart from that several laywomen too exercised their agency in multiple forms. Inscriptions are an important historical source that makes women visible on the historical stage.

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